

HYDTRENCH

- HYDFDR
- **HYDCALC**
- HYDPFL

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HYDCALC

Abstract:

This software analyzes hydraulic conduits and hydraulic channels of various shape for different parameters such as the flow, the slope, or the manning friction coefficient. This software can be used as a tool to quickly design or check the viability of a hydraulic section.

This software can be downloaded through the link below,

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/jf8vsmhhq013mdd/AACJfnUjpiiCieTCusBS0JxEa?dl=0>

HYDRAULIC CALCULATOR

Table of Contents

	<i>Page</i>
1.0 DESCRIPTION	3
2.0 MAIN MENU	7
3.0 DESIGN UNIT	9
4.0 PROJECT DATA	10
5.0 CIRCULAR CONDUIT	11
6.0 ELLIPTICAL CONDUIT	12
7.0 ARCH CONDUIT	13
8.0 RECTANGULAR CONDUIT	14
9.0 IRREGULAR CONDUIT	15
10.0 TRIANGULAR CHANNEL	16
11.0 RECTANGULAR CHANNEL	17
12.0 TRAPEZOIDAL CHANNEL	18
13.0 IRREGULAR CHANNEL	19
14.0 CIRCULAR PIPE LIBRARY	20
15.0 ELLIPTICAL PIPE LIBRARY	21
16.0 ARCH PIPE LIBRARY	22
17.0 RECTANGULAR PIPE LIBRARY	23
18.0 HELP ABOUT	24
19.0 TYPICAL PRINTED OUTPUT	25
20.0 REFERENCES	26

HYDRAULIC CALCULATOR

1.0 DESCRIPTION

The HYDCALC program was developed as a tool to help engineers quickly solve hydraulic problems of prismatic and non-prismatic geometric shapes based on the Manning formula.

$$Q = K * \frac{1}{n} * A * R_h^{2/3} * \sqrt{S}$$

Where:

Q is the flow in m^3/s (Metric units), or in ft^3/s (English units)

K is a coefficient expressed as 1.0 (Metric units), or 1.486 (English units)

n is the Manning coefficient based on the surface texture

A is the sectional area being analyzed in m^2 (Metric units), or ft^2 (English units)

R_h is the hydraulic radius or the ratio of the sectional area over the wet perimeter

S is the longitudinal slope in m/m (Metric units), or ft/ft (English units)

This program is divided in two parts, the conduit and the channel sections. For the conduit, this program will handle either a circular, elliptical, arch, rectangular, or irregular shape conduits. For the channel, the following shapes are included, triangular, rectangular, trapezoidal, and irregular. The program solves the given section using the Manning formula and presents the results graphically, displayed screen output, or printed format.

The program lists the maximum flow, the normal flow, the critical flow, and the minimum flow conditions, for either the conduit or the channel sections.

In addition, HYDCALC can handle both the Metric and the English units; and convert the data back and forth. Furthermore, this program allows the user to create his personal pipe library for non-standard sections. Each pipe section has a denomination (given name), similar or different from the actual size. This naming approach simplified the confusion sometimes associated with the Metric and English pipe names.

The amount of data (conduit or channel) that could be incorporated into a file is virtually unlimited.

The procedure created to analyze the circular, elliptical, or arch conduit is based on the principle that any of these shapes could be divided into four segments, or sectors. The procedure is based on the geometric relation of a circular sector and circular segment that are defined by the following

$$A_{sec} = \frac{\pi}{360} r^2 \alpha$$

equations.

Where:

A_{sec} is the circular sector cross sectional area in m² (Metric units), or ft² (English units)

r is the circular sector radius in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)

α is the circular sector central angle in degree

and for the circular segment,

$$A_{seg} = \frac{r^2}{2} (\alpha - \sin \alpha)$$

Where:

A_{seg} is the circular segment sectional area in m² (Metric units), or ft² (English units)

r is the circular segment radius in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)

α is the circular segment central angle in radian, and degree

For the circular conduit, the four segments will have four equal radiuses. For the elliptical conduit the two side segments have similar radius, and the top and bottom segments are the same. For the arch conduit, the top segment is different from the bottom segment. This procedure produces a much faster code, and geometrically correct analysis.

For the irregular conduit or channel (non-prismatic section), the method used to find the cross-sectional area "A" is based on the following formula.

$$A = \sum_i^{i+1} \left[\frac{(X_i - X_{i+1}) \times (Y_i + Y_{i+1})}{2} \right]$$

And for the perimeter "P"

$$P = \sum_i^{i+1} \left[(X_i - X_{i+1})^2 + (Y_i - Y_{i+1})^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

Where:

X_i is the abscissa of a point i

Y_i is the ordinate of a point i

Additionally, the approach used to calculate the composite or equivalent roughness coefficient “ n ”, is the one outlined in the HEC-RAS manual, equation 2-5.

$$n_c = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{P_i n_i^{1.5}}{P} \right)^{2/3}$$

Where:

P_i is the length of a segment i

P_T is the section wet perimeter

n_i is the Manning coefficient of a segment i

Aside from solving the Manning equation for different flow, slope, roughness coefficient or geometric section, HYDCALC also calculates the critical flow condition. The results list the critical slope, velocity, or depth of flow. This computation is based on the following relation.

$$\frac{\alpha Q^2}{G} = \frac{A^3}{T}$$

Where:

α is the velocity distribution coefficient

Q is the flow in m^3/s (Metric units), or in ft^3/s (English units)

G is the acceleration due to gravity ($9.81 m/s^2$), ($32.2 ft/s^2$)

A is the shape critical sectional area in m^2 (Metric units), or ft^2 (English units)

T is water surface width at critical depth in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)

Once the critical parameters have been calculated, the Froude number (N_f) is evaluated to determine if the flow condition is subcritical ($N_f < 1$), critical ($N_f = 1$), or supercritical ($N_f > 1$). The Froude number is calculated by using the following equation.

$$N_f = \frac{V_c}{GY_c}$$

Where:

V_c is the critical velocity in m/s (Metric units), or ft/s (English units)

G is the acceleration due to gravity (9.81 m/s²), (32.2 ft/s²)

Y_c is the critical depth in m (Metric units), or ft (English units)

In general when performing a set of computations, the user should be aware that of the applicable range of the solution being sought. The developer's intent was to create a program simple enough to use, but accurate.

2.0 MAIN MENU

A total of 16 icons are included

“NEW”

This icon will clear a project from memory.

“OPEN”

This icon will open a project file (filename.hdc).

“SAVE”

This icon will save a project file (filename.hdc).

“UNIT”

This icon will open the unit window.

“PROJECT”

This icon will open the project window.

“CIRCULAR CONDUIT”

This icon will open the circular conduit window.

“ELLIPTICAL CONDUIT”

This icon will open the elliptical conduit window.

“ARCH CONDUIT”

This icon will open the arch conduit window.

“RECTANGULAR CONDUIT”

This icon will open the rectangular conduit window.

“IRREGULAR CONDUIT”

This icon will open the irregular conduit window.

“TRIANGULAR CHANNEL”

This icon will open the triangular channel window.

“RECTANGULAR CHANNEL”

This icon will open the rectangular channel window.

“TRAPEZOIDAL CHANNEL”

This icon will open the trapezoidal channel window.

“IRREGULAR CHANNEL”

This icon will open the irregular channel window.

“PIPE LIBRARY”

This icon will open the pipe library window.

“HELP ABOUT”

This icon will open the help about window.

3.0 DESIGN UNIT

By clicking on either option, the project units will be changed, and all the data transformed accordingly.

4.0 PROJECT DATA

The image shows a screenshot of a software dialog box titled "Project". The dialog box contains a section labeled "Project Informations" with five input fields, each with a label on the left and a text box on the right. The fields are: "Project Number" with the value "567-789", "Project Location" with "MIAMI DADE", "Company Name" with "FRANCIS MITCHELL & ASSOCIATES", "Client Name" with "PORT OF MIAMI", and "Designer Name" with "FRANCIS MITCHELL". At the bottom right of the dialog box, there are two buttons: "Clear" and "OK".

Field Label	Value
Project Number	567-789
Project Location	MIAMI DADE
Company Name	FRANCIS MITCHELL & ASSOCIATES
Client Name	PORT OF MIAMI
Designer Name	FRANCIS MITCHELL

The information entered here will be displayed on the printout.

5.0 CIRCULAR CONDUIT

The user chooses a pipe size from the available library, enters the Manning coefficient, the flow, the slope, and the velocity distribution coefficient alpha.

A total of eight command buttons are available. (Typical for all subsequent conduit windows)

- “PREV” Displays the previous data.
- “NEXT” Displays the next data.
- “SOLVE” Performs the analysis, draws the sketch, and fills in the output data fields.
- “ADD” Adds a data to the last record.
- “INSERT” Inserts a data at the current record position.
- “DELETE” Deletes the current data.
- “REPORT” Sends the displayed output values to the printer.
- “OK” Close the window.

There is no limit on the amount of records a data file can have.

6.0 ELLIPTICAL CONDUIT

Elliptical Pipe

Pipe No. 1 Description CONFLICT FROM S-209 TO S-210

Input Values

Denomination 12 x 18 inch

Span 12.000 in

Rise 18.000 in

Manning 0.012

Flow 2.000 ft³/s

Slope 1.0000 %

Alpha 1.00

Output Values

A Full : 1.199 ft²

P Full : 4.006 ft

R Full : 0.299 ft

Q Full : 6.641 ft³/s

V Full : 5.540 ft/s

D Full : 18.000 in

A : 0.405 ft²

P : 1.608 ft

R : 0.252 ft

Q : 2.000 ft³/s

V : 4.939 ft/s

D : 6.639 in

V Critical : 4.021 ft/s

S Critical : 0.5850 %

D Critical : 7.772 in

V Min(HGL) : 1.668 ft/s

S Min(HGL) : 0.0907 %

D Min(HGL) : 18.000 in

Froude No. : 1.344

Flow Type is : Supercritical

Sketch

< Prev Next > Solve Add Insert Delete Report OK

This window is similar to the circular conduit window. The elliptical conduit could be either horizontal or vertical.

7.0 ARCH CONDUIT

Arch Pipe

Pipe No. 1 Description OPTIONAL PIPE SHAPE

Input Values

Denomination	28 x 20 inch
Span	28.000 in
Rise	20.000 in
Manning	0.024
Flow	2.000 ft ³ /s
Slope	0.5000 %
Alpha	1.00

Output Values

A Full	: 3.104	ft ²
P Full	: 6.450	ft
R Full	: 0.481	ft
Q Full	: 8.347	ft ³ /s
V Full	: 2.689	ft/s
D Full	: 20.000	in
A	: 0.938	ft ²
P	: 2.760	ft
R	: 0.340	ft
Q	: 2.000	ft ³ /s
V	: 2.132	ft/s
D	: 5.853	in
V Critical	: 3.054	ft/s
S Critical	: 1.4557	%
D Critical	: 4.374	in
V Min(HGL)	: 0.644	ft/s
S Min(HGL)	: 0.0287	%
D Min(HGL)	: 20.000	in
Froude No.	: 0.591	
Flow Type is	: Subcritical	

Sketch

< Prev Next > **Solve** Add Insert Delete Report OK

This window is similar to the circular conduit window.

8.0 RECTANGULAR CONDUIT

Rectangular Pipe

Pipe No. 1 Description ALTERNATE SECTION

Input Values

Denomination 36 x 36 inch

Span 36.000 in

Rise 36.000 in

Manning 0.012

Flow 2.000 ft³/s

Slope 1.0000 %

Alpha 1.00

Output Values

A Full : 9.000 ft²

P Full : 12.000 ft

R Full : 0.750 ft

Q Full : 91.995 ft³/s

V Full : 10.222 ft/s

D Full : 36.000 in

A : 0.544 ft²

P : 3.363 ft

R : 0.162 ft

Q : 2.000 ft³/s

V : 3.676 ft/s

D : 2.176 in

V Critical : 2.779 ft/s

S Critical : 0.4119 %

D Critical : 2.879 in

V Min(HGL) : 0.222 ft/s

S Min(HGL) : 0.0005 %

D Min(HGL) : 36.000 in

Froude No. : 1.521

Flow Type is : Supercritical

Sketch

< Prev Next > Solve Add Insert Delete Report OK

This window is similar to the circular conduit window.

9.0 IRREGULAR CONDUIT

The screenshot shows the 'Irregular Conduit' software window. At the top, the 'Channel No.' is 2 and the 'Description' is 'SNAPPER CREEK CRUSHED CULVERT'. The 'Input Values' section includes: Flow = 30.000 ft³/s, Slope = 0.3000 %, and Alpha = 1.120. Below this is a table of points with columns for Point, Station, Elev., and Manning. A 'Sketch' window shows a red polygon representing the conduit cross-section on a grid, with a blue horizontal line indicating the water surface. The 'Output Values' section lists various hydraulic parameters: A Full (22.000 ft²), P Full (40.190 ft), R Full (0.547 ft), Q Full (58.194 ft³/s), V Full (2.645 ft/s), D Full (6.000 ft), A (10.393 ft²), P (18.490 ft), R (0.562 ft), Q (30.000 ft³/s), V (2.887 ft/s), D (3.653 ft), V Critical (6.143 ft/s), S Critical (1.6176 %), D Critical (2.461 ft), V Min(HGL) (1.364 ft/s), S Min(HGL) (0.0797 %), D Min(HGL) (6.000 ft), and Froude No. (0.266). The 'Flow Type is' is Subcritical. At the bottom, there are navigation buttons: < Prev, Next >, Solve, Add, Insert, Delete, Report, and OK.

Point	Station	Elev.	Manning
1	1.000	7.000	0.012
2	1.000	6.000	0.012
3	3.000	1.000	0.024
4	5.000	6.000	0.024
5	7.000	1.000	0.012
6	9.000	6.000	0.012

Parameter	Value	Unit
A Full	22.000	ft ²
P Full	40.190	ft
R Full	0.547	ft
Q Full	58.194	ft ³ /s
V Full	2.645	ft/s
D Full	6.000	ft
A	10.393	ft ²
P	18.490	ft
R	0.562	ft
Q	30.000	ft ³ /s
V	2.887	ft/s
D	3.653	ft
V Critical	6.143	ft/s
S Critical	1.6176	%
D Critical	2.461	ft
V Min(HGL)	1.364	ft/s
S Min(HGL)	0.0797	%
D Min(HGL)	6.000	ft
Froude No.	0.266	
Flow Type is	Subcritical	

This window allows the user to analyze a polygonal conduit. Like the circular conduit window, the flow, the slope and the velocity distribution coefficient are required.

The polygon points are entered in term of station, elevation, and Manning coefficient. The polygon points can be manipulated, copied or pasted in other record.

A useful option in this window is when the user clicks on a point in the spreadsheet, the point position is highlighted by a black node on the sketch (see point five at the bottom right corner of the drawn section).

10.0 TRIANGULAR CHANNEL

The user enters the depth, the left and right side slope, the Manning coefficient, the flow, the slope, and the velocity distribution coefficient alpha.

A total of eight command buttons are available. (Typical for all subsequent channel windows)

- “PREV” Displays the previous data.
- “NEXT” Displays the next data.
- “SOLVE” Performs the analysis, draws the sketch, and fills in the output data fields.
- “ADD” Adds a data to the last record.
- “INSERT” Inserts a data at the current record position.
- “DELETE” Deletes the current data.
- “REPORT” Sends the displayed output values to the printer.
- “OK” Close the window.

There is no limit on the amount of record a data file can have.

11.0 RECTANGULAR CHANNEL

Channel No.
Description

Input Values		Output Values	
Width	<input type="text" value="2.000"/>	ft	
Depth	<input type="text" value="2.000"/>	ft	
H1:V		Left Side	
H1:V		Right Side	
Manning	<input type="text" value="0.024"/>		
Flow	<input type="text" value="2.000"/>	ft ³ /s	
Slope	<input type="text" value="2.0000"/>	%	
Alpha	<input type="text" value="1.00"/>		

Sketch

A Full	: <input type="text" value="4.000"/>	ft ²
P Full	: <input type="text" value="6.000"/>	ft
R Full	: <input type="text" value="0.667"/>	ft
Q Full	: <input type="text" value="26.728"/>	ft ³ /s
V Full	: <input type="text" value="6.682"/>	ft/s
D Full	: <input type="text" value="2.000"/>	ft
A	: <input type="text" value="0.605"/>	ft ²
P	: <input type="text" value="2.605"/>	ft
R	: <input type="text" value="0.232"/>	ft
Q	: <input type="text" value="2.000"/>	ft ³ /s
V	: <input type="text" value="3.307"/>	ft/s
D	: <input type="text" value="0.302"/>	ft
V Critical	: <input type="text" value="3.181"/>	ft/s
S Critical	: <input type="text" value="1.7787"/>	%
D Critical	: <input type="text" value="0.314"/>	ft
V Min(HGL)	: <input type="text" value="0.500"/>	ft/s
S Min(HGL)	: <input type="text" value="0.0112"/>	%
D Min(HGL)	: <input type="text" value="2.000"/>	ft
Froude No.	: <input type="text" value="1.060"/>	
Flow Type is	: <input type="text" value="Supercritical"/>	

<input type="button" value=" < Prev"/>	<input type="button" value=" Next >"/>	<input type="button" value=" Solve"/>	<input type="button" value=" Add"/>	<input type="button" value=" Insert"/>	<input type="button" value=" Delete"/>	<input type="button" value=" Report"/>	<input type="button" value=" OK"/>
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This window is similar to the triangular channel window.

12.0 TRAPEZOIDAL CHANNEL

Channel No. **1**
Description **DRAINAGE DITCH**

Input Values		Output Values	
Width	1.000	ft	
Depth	2.000	ft	
H1:V	1.00	Left Side	
H1:V	1.00	Right Side	
Manning	0.012		
Flow	3.000	ft ³ /s	
Slope	0.2500	%	
Alpha	1.00		

Sketch

A Full	: 6.000	ft ²
P Full	: 6.657	ft
R Full	: 0.901	ft
Q Full	: 34.662	ft ³ /s
V Full	: 5.777	ft/s
D Full	: 2.000	ft
A	: 0.963	ft ²
P	: 2.702	ft
R	: 0.357	ft
Q	: 3.000	ft ³ /s
V	: 3.114	ft/s
D	: 0.602	ft
V Critical	: 3.593	ft/s
S Critical	: 0.3694	%
D Critical	: 0.542	ft
V Min(HGL)	: 0.500	ft/s
S Min(HGL)	: 0.0019	%
D Min(HGL)	: 2.000	ft
Froude No.	: 0.830	
Flow Type is	: Subcritical	

< Prev
Next >
Solve
Add
Insert
Delete
Report
OK

This window is similar to the triangular channel window.

13.0 IRREGULAR CHANNEL

The screenshot shows the 'Irregular Channel' software window. The title bar reads 'Irregular Channel'. The 'Channel No.' is 1 and the 'Description' is 'SINK HOLE SECTION'.

Input Values:

- Flow: 250.000 ft³/s
- Slope: 2.0000 %
- Alpha: 1.000

Point	Station	Elev.	Manning
1	0.000	5.000	0.012
2	2.000	5.000	0.012
3	2.000	4.000	0.012
4	1.000	4.000	0.012
5	1.000	3.000	0.012
6	3.000	3.000	0.012

Output Values:

- A Full: 28.998 ft²
- P Full: 52.998 ft
- R Full: 0.547 ft
- Q Full: 339.707 ft³/s
- V Full: 11.715 ft/s
- D Full: 3.999 ft
- A: 21.141 ft²
- P: 38.100 ft
- R: 0.555 ft
- Q: 250.000 ft³/s
- V: 11.825 ft/s
- D: 2.591 ft
- V Critical: 10.563 ft/s
- S Critical: 1.5949 %
- D Critical: 2.953 ft
- V Min(HGL): 8.621 ft/s
- S Min(HGL): 1.0832 %
- D Min(HGL): 3.999 ft
- Froude No.: 1.295
- Flow Type is: Supercritical

The 'Sketch' area shows a grid with a red polygon representing the channel cross-section. A blue line indicates the water surface profile. The 'Solve' button is highlighted.

This window allows the user to analyze a polygonal channel. Like the irregular conduit window, the flow, the slope and the velocity distribution coefficient are required.

The polygon points are entered in term of station, elevation, and Manning coefficient. The polygon points can be manipulated, copied or pasted in other record.

A useful option in this window is when the user clicks on a point in the spreadsheet, the point position is highlighted by a black node on the sketch.

14.0 CIRCULAR PIPE LIBRARY

The screenshot shows the 'Pipe Library' software interface. At the top, a dropdown menu is set to 'Circular Pipe'. Below this, there are two main sections: 'English Unit Pipe' and 'Metric Unit Pipe'. Each section contains a table of specifications. The 'English Unit Pipe' section has a 'Denomination' of '48 inch' and values for Span, Rise, Rb, Rt, and Rc, all in inches. The 'Metric Unit Pipe' section has a 'Denomination' of '1200 mm' and values for Span, Rise, Rb, Rt, and Rc, all in millimeters. Below these sections is a 'Sketch' area showing a red circle. To the right of the sketch is the 'Pipe Properties' section, which displays 'Area' as 12.5664 ft², 'Perimeter' as 12.5664 ft, and 'Hyd. Radius' as 1.0000 ft. At the bottom of the window is a toolbar with buttons for '< Prev', 'Next >', 'Plot', 'Add', 'Insert', 'Delete', 'Report', and 'OK'.

English Unit Pipe		
Denomination	48 inch	
Span	48.00	inch
Rise	48.00	inch
Rb	24.00	inch
Rt	24.00	inch
Rc	24.00	inch

Metric Unit Pipe		
Denomination	1200 mm	
Span	1219.20	mm
Rise	1219.20	mm
Rb	609.60	mm
Rt	609.60	mm
Rc	609.60	mm

Sketch

Pipe Properties

Area	12.5664	ft ²
Perimeter	12.5664	ft
Hyd. Radius	1.0000	ft

< Prev Next > Plot Add Insert Delete Report OK

Different circular pipe conduit can be created. The data entered are dynamically converted into either the English or the Metric units.

15.0 ELLIPTICAL PIPE LIBRARY

The screenshot shows the 'Pipe Library' software window with the 'Elliptical Pipe' shape selected. The interface is divided into several sections:

- Shape:** A dropdown menu showing 'Elliptical Pipe'.
- English Unit Pipe:** A table of parameters for English units.
- Metric Unit Pipe:** A table of parameters for metric units.
- Sketch:** A drawing area showing a red ellipse.
- Pipe Properties:** A table of calculated properties.
- Buttons:** A row of control buttons at the bottom.

English Unit Pipe			Metric Unit Pipe		
Denomination	12 x 18 inch		Denomination	305 x 460 mm	
Span	12.00	inch	Span	304.80	mm
Rise	18.00	inch	Rise	457.20	mm
Rb	5.00	inch	Rb	127.00	mm
Rt	5.00	inch	Rt	127.00	mm
Rc	13.50	inch	Rc	342.90	mm

Pipe Properties		
Area	1.1988	ft ²
Perimeter	4.0062	ft
Hyd. Radius	0.2992	ft

Buttons: < Prev, Next >, Plot, Add, Insert, Delete, Report, OK

Different elliptical pipe conduit can be created. The data entered are dynamically converted into either the English or the Metric units.

Depending on the corner radius or the top and bottom radius, a vertical or a horizontal ellipse can be created.

16.0 ARCH PIPE LIBRARY

The screenshot shows the 'Pipe Library' software interface. At the top, a dropdown menu is set to 'Arch Pipe'. Below this, there are two main sections: 'English Unit Pipe' and 'Metric Unit Pipe'. Each section contains a table of parameters for an arch pipe.

English Unit Pipe		
Denomination	17 x 13 inch	
Span	17.25	inch
Rise	13.00	inch
Rb	25.63	inch
Rt	8.63	inch
Rc	3.50	inch

Metric Unit Pipe		
Denomination	450 x 340 mm	
Span	438.15	mm
Rise	330.20	mm
Rb	651.00	mm
Rt	219.20	mm
Rc	88.90	mm

Below these tables is a 'Sketch' area containing a red outline of an arch pipe. To the right of the sketch is a 'Pipe Properties' section with the following values:

Area	1.2582	ft ²
Perimeter	4.0821	ft
Hyd. Radius	0.3082	ft

At the bottom of the interface, there is a text prompt: 'Enter Pipe Corner Radius, Click Mouse To Update Value'. Below this prompt are several buttons: '< Prev', 'Next >', 'Plot', 'Add', 'Insert', 'Delete', 'Report', and 'OK'.

Different arch pipe conduit can be created. The data entered are dynamically converted into either the English or the Metric units. Because of the four segments procedure, an upside down arch section could be created.

17.0 RECTANGULAR PIPE LIBRARY

The screenshot shows the 'Pipe Library' software interface. At the top, a dropdown menu is set to 'Rectangular Pipe'. Below this, there are two main sections: 'English Unit Pipe' and 'Metric Unit Pipe'. Each section contains a table of specifications. The 'English Unit Pipe' section shows a 36 x 36 inch pipe with a span and rise of 36.00 inches, and zero values for Rb, Rt, and Rc. The 'Metric Unit Pipe' section shows a 900 x 900 mm pipe with a span and rise of 914.40 mm, and zero values for Rb, Rt, and Rc. Below these sections is a 'Sketch' area showing a red square. To the right of the sketch is the 'Pipe Properties' section, which displays the area as 9.0000 ft², the perimeter as 12.0000 ft, and the hydraulic radius as 0.7500 ft. At the bottom of the window is a toolbar with buttons for '< Prev', 'Next >', 'Plot', 'Add', 'Insert', 'Delete', 'Report', and 'OK'.

English Unit Pipe		
Denomination	36 x 36 inch	
Span	36.00	inch
Rise	36.00	inch
Rb	0.00	inch
Rt	0.00	inch
Rc	0.00	inch

Metric Unit Pipe		
Denomination	900 x 900 mm	
Span	914.40	mm
Rise	914.40	mm
Rb	0.00	mm
Rt	0.00	mm
Rc	0.00	mm

Sketch

Pipe Properties

Area	9.0000	ft ²
Perimeter	12.0000	ft
Hyd. Radius	0.7500	ft

Different rectangular pipe conduit can be created. The data entered are dynamically converted into either the English or the Metric units.

18.0 HELP ABOUT

This window displays the version, author, and copyright label. This program can be ordered as a package from the following address.

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